

WORK MOTIVATION OF GENERATION Z IN BULGARIA

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Abstract. The human factor is particularly important for the development of the information society. The young people of generation Z, who are already a significant part of the labor market, are the main generator for the development of this new society.

This study highlights the motives and social factors that affect the professional and career choices of Generation Z, taking into account the specific national characteristics of Bulgarian students and young graduates.

The statistically significant differences in the opinions of the respondents in respect to their age, gender, work experience, marital status and choice of specialty/profession are described.

The empirical study results reveal that the motivating factors (intrinsic and extrinsic) for Generation Z respondents can be summarized as: respect of opinion; financial reward; opportunity personal potential to be fulfilled; contribution to the welfare of the society; and the security offered by the profession.

Keywords: generation Z; work motivation; occupational choice; empirical research.

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1. Introduction

The Republic of Bulgaria is a country from the former Eastern Bloc. After its collapse, from the beginning of the 90s of the 20th century, it embarked on the path of democratic changes – a long and difficult path that has not yet ended.

On January 1, 2007, Bulgaria became a member of the European Union (EU). From the same date, the EU labour market is open to Bulgarian citizens without restrictions.

There are currently three generations on the labour market in Bulgaria – X generation, Y generation, Z generation. According to data from the National Statistical Institute, these groups together make up nearly 88% of the labour force in Bulgaria.

X Generation

This is the generation born from 1965 to 1979, i.e. people aged 44 to 58 years. The generation experienced the various dynamic changes of the 90s of the 20th century in Bulgaria and is of active working age during the transition to a market economy. These people invest in their development and are flexible, pragmatic and adaptable. They are technically literate. They are trained to trust authority. This generation lives in the time of the emergence of digital technologies, which they use for the most part as consumers.

Y Generation

This generation was born in the period from 1980 to 1994, i.e. people aged 29 to 43 years. They have known computer games and web technologies since childhood. Like the previous generation, this generation also lives in a period of many changes, not only technological, but also changes in the value system of Bulgarians. It is characterized by a lack of interest in institutions, a strong consumerist attitude, a “delayed maturity” expressed in delayed inclusion in the labour market, later leaving the parental home, difficult to manage and manipulate by traditional authorities.

Z Generation

These are young people born between 1995 and 2009.

The period in which people of Z Generation in Bulgaria grow up and are formed as individuals is characterized by profound changes in the social and economic situation in the

country, with frequent episodes of political instability leading to a gradual demographic decline. This period is also characterized by the ongoing processes of globalization and the rapid development of digital technologies, opening many new opportunities for work, education and entertainment to this group of young people. The unprecedented rapid development of ICT, along with its positive sides, raises questions about transhumanism, posthumanism, and social alienation. Both globally and nationally, Z Generation faces many new challenges.

What distinguishes Z Generation from the previous two is the fact that its representatives have always had access to digital technologies throughout their lives, from their earliest childhood. Technologies are an inalienable part of their lives; technologies make everything happen quickly and easily. Information can be searched quickly, shopping can be done quickly, and communication with others can be done quickly. This model of “quick and easy”, young people unknowingly (or consciously?) transfer to real life situations – expectation for quick results from work, for immediate praise for the efforts put in, for high pay for their work.

Today, young people from Z Generation represent 14.8% of the labour force in the labour market in Bulgaria. In the coming years, of course, their number will grow.

They will be a serious challenge for employers, who will have to change their usual HR practices to attract and use the potential of this new group of workers. The representatives of Z Generation can be a source of innovation, creativity and flexibility for the Bulgarian labour market. For this reason, they should be studied in more detail.

Work motivation is the impulse that drives people to act to achieve their goals. Motivational factors that can be highlighted include: stability (holding the same job for life); financial security; job security; pay; rewards and benefits; job and goal challenges; employment (building a career in different companies); freedom; autonomy; work schedule flexibility; status and power; in addition to the continuous search for quality of life (Draft 2010).

Work motivation is key to work engagement (Colquitt et al. 2011).

Self-determination theory (SDT) is often used to explain the factors, influencing motivation. In respect to motivation SDT distinguishes between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. According to SDT intrinsic motivation comprises motivational goals such as interest in the respective professional domain, interest in human relationships, helping people, and seeking significance. Intrinsic motivation depends on the attainment of three basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness, which in turn foster the most salient and high-quality forms of motivation and commitment to activities, including improved performance, persistence, and creativity. In addition, SDT suggests that the extent to which any of these three psychological needs are unsupported or are impeded in a social context will have a highly detrimental impact on well-being in that environment.

The extrinsic motives most commonly identified are: career; financial security; prestige and social status (Holzer et al. 2022).

1.1 Aim, objectives and hypothesis of the study

Research on work motivation and professional choice attitudes of Generation Z globally has grown during the recent years (Nabahani and Riyanto 2020; Septiawan and Masrunik 2020; Gaidhani at all. 2019; Mahmoud at all. 2021). Similar topics are also the subject of research interest in Bulgaria, but they usually address these issues partially (Eftimova at all. 2022), and empirical data on the actual state of the art are still lacking.

The present survey was conducted in the period 12-20 April 2023.

The aim of the empirical study is to identify, analyse and summarize the motives, psycho-emotional and social factors determining the choice of workplace of the representatives of Generation Z.

The objectives of this study are to outline:

1. The social engagement of young people in their choice of profession;
2. The degree and importance of personal convenience and comfort in choice of profession.

In defining the aim and objectives of the study, the following working hypothesis are derived:

There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of different age subgroups; of respondents of both genders; of respondents from different specialties.

1.2 Object, subject, statistical methods used

The object of the study are representatives of Generation Z in the Republic of Bulgaria. In order to achieve homogeneity of the sample, the subjects are students or graduates of higher education in the age group 19 - 28 years.

The subject of the study is the effect of the following factors on the choice of young people: gender, age, previous work experience (or lack of experience), education, marital status, specialty.

CMQ: Career Motivation Questionnaire/ Career Motivation Test and Life Goals questionnaire were studied in detail when compiling the questionnaire. The items in the present questionnaire were tailored to their main directions. It was decided not to administer these questionnaires in their full, authentic form, but a modified scale to be developed for the purpose of this study.

The following statistical methods are applied:

Descriptive statistics;

Univariate analysis of variance;

Univariate frequency distribution of data;

Correlation analysis.

Cronbach's alpha was calculated to check the internal consistency.

The normality of the respondents' answers is checked. The norms of Kurtosis and Skewness values are taken into account.

Crosstabs and Pearson's Chi-Square test are applied to check gender differences.

1.3 Scope and limitations of the study

The general population of the study comprises 310 volunteers, undergraduate students in bachelor's and master's degrees, as well as graduates. Due to the search for a more representative and accurate sample, the survey does not cover students in schools.

Given the different interpretations and conceptions regarding the age frame of Generation Z, for the purposes of this study, 1995 is chosen as the most optimal lower bound (Katz 2021; McCrindle 2014).

The scale was designed for the purposes of this particular survey. It includes a total of 18 items - 17 closed-ended questions and one semi-open-ended question. A 5-point Likert scale was used as self-report scale, given the subsequent processing of the data obtained with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) v19 software product.

The data collection was done through traditional administration format (paper-and-pencil) and field visit to two universities - University of Library Studies and Information Technologies (ULSIT) - Sofia and Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski.

Most of the respondents (284) are undergraduates / graduates from ULSIT. Undergraduates /graduates of Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" are 26 studying/graduated Medicine.

This study mainly presents the attitudes and motives of students studying at ULSUT.

The sample of respondents from the medical specialty of SU is used for comparison both between young people who chose different specialties and between the two groups of graduates of different universities.

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are presented in the following table. The *univariate frequency distribution method* was applied in the calculation.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Indicators	N	Percent (%)
Age		
19 – 21 y.o.	146	47.1
22 – 24 y.o.	102	32.9
25 – 28 y.o.	62	20.0
Total	310	100.0
Gender		
Woman	168	54.2
Man	142	45.8
Total	310	100.0
Length of service		
No length of service	98	31,6
Up to 3 years	140	45.2
More than 3 years	72	23.2
Total	310	100.0
Work experience in the specialty in which the student is trained or has graduated		
No length of service	214	69.0
Up to 3 years	78	25.2
More than 3 years	18	5.8
Total	310	100.0
Marital status		
Married	36	11.6
Cohabitation	106	34.2
Single	168	54.2
Divorced	-	-
Total	310	100.0
Educational status		
Undergraduate, bachelor's degree	256	82.6
Undergraduate, master's degree	8	2.6
Higher (Bachelor)	14	4.5
Higher (Master)	26	8.4
Higher (PhD)	6	1.9
Total	310	100.0

The sampling design aimed at a wider range of occupations preferred by Generation Z representatives. For this reason, the survey covers both fundamental and applied specialties. The professional fields in which they are training or have graduated are as follows:

"Public Communications and Information Sciences" - n =112 (36.1%);

"Informatics and Computer Science" - n =98 (31.6%);

"History and Archaeology" - n =20 (6.5%);

"Medicine" - n =26 (8.4%);

"National Security" n =54 (17.4%).

The univariate frequency distribution method is also applied to summarise the responses to Item 18. "Who/what motivated/guided you to choose the major you are studying?" The results are as follows: the highest number is of respondents who made their own choice of major - 238 (76.8%). For 52 (16.8%) of the respondents the choice had been influenced by parents and/or relatives, and 20 (6.4%) had followed the opinion of friends (Figure 1). It is noteworthy that young people in Bulgaria are still reluctant to trust career counselling centres.

Fig. 1. Persons who influenced the choice of specialty

1.4 Items and variables

Since occupational choice motives include both intrinsic and extrinsic factors (Barhate and Dirani 2022), the motives for choosing a satisfying occupation in the present study include 2 subscales - Intrinsic satisfaction (Items 2; 3; 6; 7; 10; 11;12; 14); Extrinsic satisfaction (Items 1; 4; 5; 8; 9; 13; 15; 16; 17).

1. The physical working conditions
2. The ability to work alone, to be independent
3. The prestige of the profession in society
4. The freedom to choose my own working method
5. The colleagues I would have the opportunity to work with
6. The recognition for a job well done
7. The flexible working hours
8. The social realisation that the profession implies
9. The amount of the salary
10. The opportunity to fulfil my potential
11. The opportunity my performance to contribute to society
12. The chance to advance in the hierarchy
13. The opportunity to work abroad

14. The respect of my opinion
15. The variety of tasks that the profession entails
16. The security that the profession gives
17. The remote work opportunity

1.5 Reliability of the data

In the analysis of the results, the data distribution normality was tested.

The norms of Kurtosis and Skewness values were taken into account.

The Skewness and Kurtosis coefficients are within the normal range except for the characteristics relating to the educational status of the respondents. Since there are only eight respondents studying for a Master's degree and only six respondents who have obtained a PhD, their results will not be reflected in the comparative analysis of the education factor.

Table 2. Reliability check of demographic data (Skewness and Kurtosis)

Demographic indicators	Skewness	Kurtosis
Age	.51	-1.15
Gender	.17	-1.99
Total work experience	.13	-1.14
Work experience	1.38	.89
Marital status	-.04	-1.18
Education	2.15	2.62
Specialty / specialty graduated	.77	-.87

1.6 Construct reliability analysis

The internal consistency reliability of the Bivariate Job Selection Motivation Scale, comprising 18 items, was assessed based on the analysis of the average inter-item correlation (AIC) between the statements and the calculation of Cronbach's Alpha.

The mean inter-statement correlation analysis for the Scale is 0.304 (Table 3).

Table 3. Average Inter-item Correlation
Summary Item Statistics

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Means	3.778	2.729	4.374	1.645	1.603	.202	18
Inter-Item Correlations	.304	-.176	.667	.843	-3.792	.024	18

The internal consistency of the items in the scale, examining Generation Z youth's motives for choosing a job, as statistically measured by Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.887$), is high.

2. Results

2.1 Analysis of the results by age groups

In view to data processing, the general population of the study is divided into three age subgroups as follows: 18-21 years; 22-24 years; 25-28 years.

The working hypothesis is that there are statistically significant differences between the subgroups. It is also a working hypothesis that there is a significant correlation between age and employment of the respondents.

In analysing the results it is evident that both extrinsic and intrinsic motivational factors are important for the respondents, irrespective of the age subgroup they belong to.

However, the importance attached to them by younger respondents usually differs significantly (statistically significant difference greater than 0.05).

Respondents in the 18-21 and 22-24 age groups are more sensitive to the surrounding work environment (both physical and emotional, given interpersonal relationships with colleagues). Respondents in the 25 - 28 age group, who are also already working, including with work experience in their chosen specialty, are more moderate in their demands. For them, the recognition of a job well done, i.e. the evaluation of the final result of their work, is of primary importance as an extrinsic motivation factor (M=4.26).

The desire for independence in work is also stronger among younger respondents, as is respect for their opinions (M=4.34 for 18-21 year olds and M=4.33 for 22-24 year olds). For them, it is more important that their profession enjoys social prestige. At the same time as the observed, characteristic of young people, desire for independence, to manage their time (flexible working hours - M=4.05 for 18 - 21 year olds and M=4.08 for 22 - 24 year olds), it is evident that they are not willing to compromise with the pay for their work (M=4.33 for 18 - 21 year olds and M=4.37 for 22 - 24 year olds). There is a significant statistical difference between the opinion of these two subgroups of respondents and that of those in the 25 - 28 age group - M=4.19. The pay as a motivating factor replicates data obtained from another similar study - that of representatives of Generation Z from Slovakia - a country which, like Bulgaria, was part of the former socialist bloc (Kirchmayer and Fratricová 2020). Until 1989, wage differentials were not significant. After the democratic changes that began in 1990, opportunities for better incomes became real and, unfortunately, became an aim in itself for many people in these countries. Salary increases alone quickly lose their motivating power as employees become accustomed to change in a short time (Judge et al. 2010).

Remote learning, respectively remote working, is particularly preferred by the youngest respondents, whose learning process and life in general has been mediated to the greatest extent by new technologies M=3.68 for 18-21 year olds. Although their responses cover the whole range of the scale (from 1 to 5), no high or very high values prevail, i.e. there is no persistent attitude of preference for remote working.

While all respondents fall into the Generation Z age group, the differences in their responses predictably indicate that other factors such as life experience, work experience, gender and marital status are also relevant.

2.2 Analysis of the results obtained by gender of respondents

Table 4. Motives for choosing a job /gender factor/

Tested dependant variables	N	M	SD	F	Sig
Physical working conditions	women (n=168)	3.35	1.16	.46	.49
	men (n=142)	3.48	1.26		
Ability to work alone, to be independent	women (n=168)	3.81	1.08	4.02	.04
	men (n=142)	3.45	1.14		
Prestige of the profession in society	women (n=168)	3.44	1.14	.150	.699
	men (n=142)	3.37	1.24		
Freedom to choose my own working method	women (n=168)	4.00	1.05	5.03	.02
	men (n=142)	3.59	1.21		
Colleagues I would have the opportunity to work with	women (n=168)	3.92	1.02	1.01	.31
	men (n=142)	3.73	1.25		
Recognition for a job well done	women (n=168)	4.19	1.13	4.72	.03
	men (n=142)	3.83	.96		
Flexible working hours	women (n=168)	4.12	1.12	.78	.37
	men (n=142)	3.96	1.13		
Social realisation that the profession implies	women (n=168)	4.11	1.06	6.58	.01
	men (n=142)	3.61	1.36		
Amount of the salary	women (n=168)	4.39	.94	1.14	.20
	men (n=142)	4.23	1.00		
Opportunity to fulfil my potential	women (n=168)	4.42	.86	.42	.51
	men (n=142)	4.32	.89		
Opportunity my performance to contribute to society	women (n=168)	3.98	1.06	2.16	.14
	men (n=142)	3.70	1.23		
Chance to advance in the hierarchy	women (n=168)	4.02	1.04	2.01	.15
	men (n=142)	3.76	1.27		
Opportunity to work abroad	women (n=168)	3.04	1.40	2.38	.12
	men (n=142)	2.70	1.23		
Respect of my opinion	women (n=168)	4.37	.91	1.48	.22
	men (n=142)	4.20	.82		
Variety of tasks that the profession entails	women (n=168)	4.02	1.04	3.65	.05
	men (n=142)	3.70	1.03		
Security that the profession gives	women (n=168)	4.27	1.01	3.11	.08
	men (n=142)	3.97	1.12		
Remote work opportunity	women (n=168)	3.75	1.24	2.41	.12
	men (n=142)	3.42	1.38		

It is evident from the results presented in Table 6 that across all the motivation factors (both intrinsic and extrinsic) examined, the values for females are higher. A statistically significant difference with higher values for male respondents is observed in the response to the question on the importance of physical working conditions (M=3.35 for females; M=3.48 for males).

Crosstab is applied to refine the result regarding the importance of financial remuneration when considering the gender of the respondents. From the data obtained (Table 5), it is clear that

the answers in the higher ranks (fifth and fourth) are given in a higher percentage by women, and that women are less likely to hesitate (only 6 women /3.9%/ gave the answer "both yes and no" against 11 men /7.1%/). This necessitated the testing of the working hypothesis with a Chi-Square test (Chi-Square test - Table 6).

Table 5. Importance of financial reward in the choice of workplace /gender factor/. Crosstab

gender	no impact	low impact	both has and has no impact	high impact	very high impact	total
Women respondents N and %	2 1.3%	3 1.9%	6 3.9%	22 14.2%	51 32.9%	84 54,2%
men respondents N and %	3 1.9%	0 0%	11 7.1%	21 13,5%	36 23.2%	71 45.8%
total	5 3.2%	3 1.9%	17 11.0%	43 27.7%	87 56.1%	155 100%

Table 6. Significance of financial reward in job choice /gender factor/. Chi-Square test

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymp.Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.234 ^a	4	.182
Likelihood Ratio	7.384	4	.117
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.143	1	.285
N of Valid Cases	310		

a. 4 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.37.

The value of the test statistic is 6.234.

The footnote for this statistic refers to an assumption for an expected number of cells greater than 4.

Since the test statistic is based on Crosstab 3x2, the degrees of freedom (df) for the test statistic is 4.

The corresponding p-value of the test statistic is $p = 0.182$.

Since the p-value is greater than our chosen significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), we do not reject the null hypothesis. Rather, we conclude that there is insufficient evidence to suggest a relationship between gender and reward significance.

Based on the results, we can conclude the following:

No strong relationship is found between gender and the importance of financial reward ($X^2(2) > 6.234$, $p = 0.182$).

2.3 Analysis of the results by respondents' work experience

The results of the study on the impact of lack of work experience reveal that there is a statistically significant difference between the responses of respondents without work experience and those who are already working. There is a higher level of both extrinsic and intrinsic motivation for those representatives of Generation Z who are already working.

The only statistically significant difference between respondents' responses is not observed for the question on the importance of respect for personal opinion recognition, but this question is more in principle.

There is also a statistically significant difference between the views of respondents who have no work experience in their specialty and those who are already working in their chosen specialty.

Respondents with more than 3 years of work experience have significantly fewer requirements regarding the physical work environment ($M = 3.00$) than those who do not yet have such work experience ($M = 3.33$).

Those already working in their specialty tend to somewhat neglect their desire for independence ($M = 3.22$)/for those not working ($M = 3.69$).

The prestige of their profession in society is no longer as important to those in work ($M = 2.89$); the statistically significant difference on this indicator between those in work and those not in work is high - ($M = 3.44$).

They also have lower demands for the freedom to choose their own method of work ($M = 3.44$); for non-workers this mean is significantly higher ($M = 3.90$).

Opportunity to fulfil my potential; Opportunity my performance to contribute to society; Chance to advance in the hierarchy; Security that the profession gives have significantly higher values. There is a slight predominance of the influence of factors of intrinsic motivation compared to those of extrinsic motivation. This indicates an awareness and development based on life experience and working in a real environment.

The marital status of the respondents is also a factor that influences their motivation to work. Statistically significant differences are observed for the three subgroups of Generation Z volunteers: - single, married and married.

From the overall view of the data, it is clear that the lowest values are for the married. It is likely that a larger proportion are in the 25 - 28 age group as well, as the results are somewhat similar to those of the 25 - 28 age group. Married respondents are the most moderate in their expectations, followed by the single. The highest values are found among the married. This is probably due to young people's desire to successfully combine the emotional personal life and the career.

2.4 Analysis of results obtained by respondents' specialties

Particularly interesting are the results for representatives of the different specialties/professions.

In the commentary and analysis of the obtained results we will consider separately the respondents from the specialty "Medicine", since they are representatives of a different university from ULSIT - SU "St. Kliment Ohridski". From the obtained data it is clear that the students in Medicine are the most balanced in their expectations - they do not feed expectations for remote work, for flexible working hours or freedom to choose their own method of work. Their profession does not imply responses with very high values to these items. Answers in the high ranges (above 4) are observed for them in terms of using and fulfilling personal potential and in terms of progression in the work hierarchy - i.e. they are aware and ambitious young people.

The most demanding in terms of physical working conditions are the respondents from the National Security specialty. This is probably because they are expected to work under greater psychic stress and thus the environment - physical and emotional in the work team should be reliable. The prestige of the profession in the society is among the main motives in choosing a specialty for them ($M = 3.70$), as well as Recognition for a job well done ($M = 4.07$), Social

realization (M=4.11), the Opportunity to contribute to the welfare of society (M=4.00). Desire for advancement in the hierarchy is most pronounced in them - (M=4.15); they are also most sensitive to having their opinions respected (M=4.52). In their choice of occupation, they are influenced to the highest degree of all respondents by the motive of security that the occupation provides (M=4.48).

For respondents in the History and Archaeology occupational field, the status of the variables studied is as follows: Ability to work alone, to be independent (M=4.00); Flexible working hours (M=4.20); Ability to use my potential (M=4.50); Ability to contribute to the good of society (M=4.10). Job security (M=4.10) and remote work opportunity (M=3.80) are also among the top motives for choosing a profession.

At the same time, they have the lowest willingness to work abroad (M=2.20) and this is understandable - their strongest advantage is the study and research of their native history and archaeology; this implies that they stay working in Bulgaria.

For the respondents from the professional field Computer Science, the main motivation factors are: Flexible working hours (M=4.04); Amount of the salary (M=4.39); Opportunity to fulfil my potential (M=4.20); Respect for opinion (M=4.14); Security that the profession gives (M=4.10) and The possibility of distant work (M=3.76). We can see that external factors dominate in their motivation. Given that computer professionals are among the most in demand today, it is understandable why this is so. The results obtained are comparable to those of similar studies (Bulut 2021).

Among the strongest motivating factors for respondents in the Social Sciences occupational field are Freedom to choose my own working method (M=4.10); Recognition for a job well done (M=4.27); Flexible working hours (M=4.30); Social realisation that the profession implies (M=4.14); Opportunity to fulfil my potential (M=4.57); Opportunity my performance to contribute to society (M=4.14); Financial reward (M=4.39); Security that the profession provides (M=4.16).

At the same time compared to the other respondents they do not assess advancement in the hierarchy particularly high (M=3.89).

They also predominantly indicate the highest values of motivating factors in general. They value their time to the highest degree, but they are also altruistic - they are most willing to contribute to the welfare of the society.

It is evident that both extrinsic and intrinsic motivation is important for them.

2.5 Correlation analysis

In the analysis of the obtained results for the both scales for the evaluation of the responses, Pearson's correlation coefficient (R) and Spearman's correlation coefficient (R) are taken into account.

The correlation between Item 2. "Ability to work alone, to be independent" and Item 4. Freedom to choose my own working method. The results are presented in Table 7. A significant positive correlation is found on a Pearson scale ($r = .667$)

Table 7. Correlations between items 2 and 4. Pearson correlation

No	Items	2	4
2	Desire for independence	*	.667**
4	Choice of own working method	.667**	*

** Significance level 0.01.

Respondents are driven by a desire for independence in choosing their own method of work.

A significant degree of correlation between these two items was also found on a Spearman scale (non-parametric) - ($r = .623^{**}$). The results are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Correlations between items № 2 and № 4. Spearman correlation

№	Items	2	4
2	Desire for independence	*	.623**
4	Choice of own working method	.623**	*

** Significance level 0.01.

Respondents relate their desire for independence to choosing their own method of work, respectively taking responsibility for this choice.

Table 9. Correlations between items № 6 and № 8. Pearson correlation

№	Items	6	8
6	Recognition	*	.393**
8	Social realization	.393**	*

** Significance level 0.01.

Pearson correlation found is moderate (Table 9).

A moderate degree of correlation between these two items was also found on a Spearman scale (non-parametric) - ($r = .318^{**}$). The results are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Correlations between items № 6 and № 8. Spearman correlation

№	Items	6	8
6	Recognition	*	.318**
8	Social realization	.318**	*

** Significance level 0.01.

Respondents perceive the recognition they receive from others as a factor directly related to their social realization.

The correlation between three of the items, suggesting extrinsic motivation, are also examined. There is a moderate to significant positive correlation. The results are presented respectively in Table 11.

Table 11. Correlations among items № 3, № 12 and № 16. Pearson correlation

№	Items	3	12	16
3	Prestige of the profession in society	*	.483**	.437**
12	Advancement in the professional hierarchy	.483**	*	.473**
16	The security that the profession provides	.437**	.573**	*

** Significance level 0.01.

Table 12. Correlations among items № 3, № 12 and № 16. Spearman correlation

№	Items	3	12	16
3	Prestige of the profession in society	*	.460**	.410**
12	Advancement in the professional hierarchy	.460**	*	.498**
16	The security that the profession provides	.410**	.498**	*

** Significance level 0.01.

The Spearman correlation among items № 3, № 12, and № 16 is also tested. The found moderate non-parametric correlation provides information about the importance of extrinsic factors in the choice of major and future profession. Young people are definitely ambitious - they associate their professional choice with the prestige of the profession in the society, the security that the chosen profession is supposed to ensure and the opportunity to advance in the hierarchy. The results are presented in Table 12.

1. Discussion and conclusion

All respondents fall into the Generation Z age group, but the differences in their responses predictably suggest that other factors such as social experience, personal preferences, work experience, gender and marital status, are also important for career preferences.

In analysing the results, it is clear that both extrinsic and intrinsic motivational factors are important for the respondents, regardless of the age subgroup they fall into.

However, the importance attached to them by younger respondents tends to differ markedly.

The desire for independence at work is also more pronounced among younger respondents, as is respect for their opinions (in the 18-21 and 22-24 age groups). For them, it is more important that their profession enjoys social prestige. At the same time as the observed characteristic of these young people, desire for independence, to manage their time, it is evident that they are not willing to compromise with the remuneration of their work. There is a significant statistical difference between the opinion of these two subgroups of respondents and that of those in the 25-28 age group - they are more moderate in their expectations.

Taking into account the gender of the respondents, it can be concluded that female respondents tend to have higher demands both on themselves and on their future/current workplace.

Another significant difference between the opinions of respondents is observed when comparing the responses of young people who do not have work experience in the specialty and those who are already working in their chosen specialty. In the case of those already working, there is some predominance of the influence of intrinsic motivation factors at the expense of extrinsic motivation factors. This indicates an awareness and development based on life experience and working in a real environment.

Differences in respondents' marital status are also relevant in ranking motives for choosing a major/profession. Married respondents are the most moderate in their expectations, followed by the single respondents. Expectations and requirements are highest for the tied. This is probably due to young people's desire to successfully combine emotional life and career.

The chance of advancement in the career hierarchy is more important for respondents in the 25-28 age group, as well as for those already in the workforce with more than 3 years of experience. This corresponds with Arthur, Hall and Lawrence's definition of a career, who define

a career as "a person's evolving sequence of work experiences over time" (Arthur and Lawrence 1996)

Career progression, the data suggest, is also of particular importance to those studying/working in the professional fields of Medicine and National Security.

Of particular interest are the results on the motives of respondents from the different professional fields included in this study.

The most demanding to physical working conditions are respondents from the specialty National Security. This is probably because they are expected to work under greater psychic stress and the environment - physical and emotional in the work team - should be reliable.

In their choice of occupation they are influenced to the highest degree of all other respondents by the motive of security that the occupation provides.

For respondents who have chosen to study/graduate Medicine, the key motivating factors include: discovering and realising one's personal potential, as well as progression up the career hierarchy - i.e. these are self-aware and ambitious young people.

Respondents from the professional field History and Archaeology almost lack the desire to work abroad and this is understandable - their competence is to study and research of native history and archaeology; this implies that they will pursue career in Bulgaria. It is particularly characteristic of the respondents from the Computer Science professional field that their motivation is dominated by extrinsic factors.

The young people who have chosen to study/graduate in the Social Sciences professional field value their time to the highest degree, but they are also altruistic - they want to contribute to society to the highest degree.

It is striking that, in contrast to data in other studies (Fantini and Naiara; Kraidenkov and Sviridova 2021), a significantly higher proportion of young people from Generation Z seek job security. This is probably due to the fact that the transition from a totalitarian to a democratic society lasted too long in Bulgaria. The unemployment rate among young people is still high. According to the National Statistical Institute of the Republic of Bulgaria for the first quarter of 2023, it is 14.8% for young people up to the age of 34. It is significantly lower for graduates (1.6% of the total number of unemployed young people).

The global economic crisis, the war in Ukraine, the lack of a regularly elected government are also factors that affect the economic situation of our country and the lack of jobs for young people.

In conclusion: The general motivating factors of the respondents from generation Z can be highlighted in the following order:

- Respect for opinion;
- Financial reward;
- Opportunity to fulfil personal potential;
- Contribution to the welfare of the society;
- Security that the profession gives.

In summary: self-respect and authority, desire for self-realisation and security, contribution to the welfare of the society while taking into account the financial reward.

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